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**COMPETENCE IN HEALTH AND SAFETY
AS AN INSEPARABLE PART OF A TEACHER'S
PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE**

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**КОМПЕТЕНТНІСТЬ З БЕЗПЕКИ ЖИТТЄДІЯЛЬНОСТІ
ЯК НЕВІД'ЄМНИЙ СКЛАДНИК ПРОФЕСІЙНОЇ
КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТІ ВЧИТЕЛЯ**

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The article reveals the essence and the contents of the concepts «the professional teacher's competence» and «the competence in the area of teacher's health and safety» from the point of view of different scientists, the role of a teacher in shaping of safety culture of students. The article states the functional components of teachers' activity in the area of health and safety.

It has been determined that the notion «professional competence» is a complex of human knowledge and abilities to perform certain professional functions. The notion «competence in the health and safety» is an integrated characterization of professional and personal capacities of an expert, which is based on the amount of knowledge, abilities and skills acquired in the process of continuous education in the area of health and safety and also includes the implementation methods and techniques of health and safety system in the professional activities.

The professional competence in the area of health and safety is related to the group of key competences of the individual in general and professional competences of a modern teacher in particular.

The article demonstrates the structure of competence of teacher's health and safety stipulated by the peculiarities of her professional activity and components (motivational, cognitive, activity and reflexive).

Key words: competence, health and safety, teacher, professional competence, competence in the area of health and safety.

The Outline of the Problem. The Child Rights Convention, passed by the United Nations Organization in 1989 foresees that the states-participants, including Ukraine, provide survival and healthy maturity of a child at a maximum possible degree. Yet in modern conditions of aggressive environment the fulfillment of the Convention provisions is possible only if children have formed the culture of health and safety. Effective knowledge of the culture of safety can be obtained by a specific educational process that provides a purposeful training of students for prevention and helps to overcome the influence of harmful and dangerous environmental factors in the process of specially organized creative cooperation between the students and a teacher that is a safety culture bearer [1, p. 30]

Modern education has to become a national resource for the social life renovation; it has to be a mechanism of a social development monitoring and safety. That is why the discussion of the question of a teacher's professionalism, development of his/her culture of health and safety is a necessary condition of the existence of a «safe power».

One of the main ways of education reforming results in the necessity to train a new generation of teachers and to improve their professional and cultural levels. That is why teachers should have a high level of professional competence in the area of health and safety as an integral component of their activity.

Analysis of the main researches and publications which initiate the solution of the given problem. Health and safety is being considered by experts at the state level as well as at some researches, it includes some theoretical provisions, axioms, methods of research of different branches of knowledge that create the general science of Safety.

Thus, health and safety experts Ye. Arustamov, Ye. Zhelibo, N. Zaveruha, V. Zatsarniy, D. Zerkalov, S. Marova have made a considerable contribution into the development of health and safety as a science.

The research works of teachers S. Hvozdiy, L. Horyana, O. Pulyak, A. Tymchenko, Ye. Chernyshova and others devoted to the aspects of teaching schoolchildren and students the health and safety basics, formation of future

teachers' competence in health and safety are interesting for us in a practical perspective [5; 7; 9; 12; 13].

Domestic scientists-teachers Yu. Boichuck, L. Karpova, Ye. Chernishova, K. Jur'eva have released a detailed analysis of a teacher's professional competence phenomenon, revealed its structural elements, particularities and elaborated its systems of development [3; 7; 8; 14].

We know certain works [1; 4; 9; 13], that focus on the process of the continuous education in the area of the teacher's health and safety, but the potential of the competence approach has not been used to the full. There are no researches dealing with the process of teachers' competence development in the area of health and safety in the system of postgraduate pedagogical education.

The aim of the article is the definition of the concept of competence in the area of the teacher's health and safety as an inseparable part of a teacher's professional competence, its contents and structural components.

Presentation of the Main Material. It is a question of an urgent need to train the rising generation for independent safety life in the epoch of extreme situations, cataclysms, threats. A healthy nation upbringing with formed health and safety culture, with mastered algorithm of actions in the specific extreme situations is one of the primary tasks the educational science is facing now.

As the basic priorities, motivations, world outlook, directions on to a certain way of life are formed during childhood and youth, that is why preschool and general educational institutions, that train a considerable number of children and school youth during a long period of time face the task to teach the rising generation to lead a regular life, to teach the students the rules of a safety way of life that could help them take care of their health and strengthen it. The need of continuous and uninterrupted work in this direction stipulates the necessity of search of effective pedagogical technologies, strategies, adequate to individual peculiarities, age and social status of the students, development and implementation of all-embracing preventive measures at educational institutions [13].

There is a well-acknowledged statement in pedagogics about the primary role of a teacher's personality in the child shaping, including teaching the pupils how to form abilities and skills in the area of health and safety.

Such state documents as The Constitution of Ukraine, the laws of Ukraine «On Education», «On General Secondary Education», «On Higher Education» and normative legal acts of safety define the prospects of the modern education

development and the teachers' role in forming in children and school youth knowledge in the area of health and safety.

Deep learning of the content competence in the area of teacher's health and safety requires from us the analysis of the concept «professional competence» from different approaches of scientific literature, namely: it is the totality of professional knowledge, skills as well as ways of fulfillment of professional activity; professional competence contains knowledge, abilities, skills as well as ways and methods of their implementation in action, communication and development of a personality.

We agree with the opinion of respected researchers N. Bibik, L. Vashchenko, O. Lokshyna, O. Ovcharuk, that the competence always results in activity. Teacher's professional competence in particular is manifested while solving professional tasks, the context being of the primary importance, by means of which the specific competence becomes evident. However, there is no unanimous opinion concerning explanation and use of these definitions [8].

Thus, the concept «professional competence» is wider than the knowledge, abilities and skills, it doesn't make their sum, because it involves all the aspects of activity: knowledge-oriented, operational technological, value – motivated etc. Paying attention to the researches of L. Karpova, who believes that methodological, practical active, didactic methodical, special scientific and economical legal, ecological, valeological, informational and executive competence, belong to operational technological sphere of a teacher's professional competence, we add competence of health and safety which should be an inseparable part of a teacher's competence of any speciality [7] to the given structure. Such competence is formed as a result of training and gaining experience at all the stages of education and a person's practical activity.

It is understandable that the level of professional competence of teachers in the area of health and safety in a certain measure depends on the level that was formed during their study at a higher school. However, we can consider a person educated if he/she can control the process of gaining knowledge, skills and competence during their whole life. According to this approach the system of the postgraduate pedagogical education becomes the most important educational link in improving specialists' qualification and further training. That is why the functions of postgraduate education – from serving, accompanying to forestalling, prognostic are being radically changed.

For example, in the researches by O. Teleschak competence in the area of health and safety is an integrated result of the educational activity of students

that is based on the sum of knowledge, gained in the process of education in the area of health and safety while learning special disciplines («Health and safety», «Valeology», «Health and Safety in a Branch», «Civil Protection») and disciplines of psychological pedagogical and fundamental training. This result reveals through the skills necessary for modern life, readiness of a person to act in various life situations, ability and preparedness to achieve more qualitative result of activity [11].

M. Geraskina [6], a scientist researched the phenomenon of professional competence of general educational institutions staff in the area of personal health and safety of students, that contains an idea of the methods of revealing general and specific threats, their prevention and neutralization, as well as ability to improve their professional activity in this branch.

Ye. Rebko and V. Anyschenko offer more detailed definition of professional teacher's competence in health and safety [10]:

– the type of professional result that is based on a fundamental scientific education is a precondition of preparedness for creative solution of educational tasks designing and accomplishing cognitive and value-orientated activity of a person with a behaviour of a safety type;

– systemic realization of formed professionally important regulations and personal qualities, theoretical knowledge and practical skills concerning health and safety; ability to effectively organize an educational process in the area of health and safety in accordance with modern principles and demands.

To understand the essence of professional competence in health and safety of a modern educational institution teacher we should outline a number of demands and tasks for a teacher to deal with during his professional activity.

In «The Provision on the Organization of Work in the Area of Health and Safety of the Participants of Educational Upbringing Process» confirmed by the order of Ministry of Education and Science № 563 from 01.08.2001, there is a defined role of an educationalist in the organization of work for health and safety in an educational institution, namely: *he has a responsibility for health and safety of the students in the process of their education and upbringing; provides the process of education and training, that is regulated by special legislative and normative legal acts of labour protection, health and safety; organizes the students' study of rules and norms of health and safety; implements instructing of health and safety during the studies, extra-curricular activities outside and inside the school premises (entrance, primary, extraordinary and purposeful); implements control over students' fulfillment the rules (instructions)*

of safety; *carries out preventive work* concerning traumatism during educational upbringing process; *carries out preventive work* among the students concerning demands of personal life safety (actions in extreme situations, road traffic, participation in mass measures, stay in public places, trade network establishments etc); *organizes* first aid [2, p.120].

To provide the mentioned demands a teacher has to renew and check his/her professional knowledge of health and safety once every three years (Order of the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine, № 304 from 18.04.2006) and continually heighten her professional level according to the today's demands [2, p.46].

Analysis and synthesis of different approaches to the defining of competence in health and safety allows us to define it as an integrated characteristics of professional and personal qualities, orientations of value and ability of a specialist reflection, that is based on the totality of knowledge, skills and abilities, obtained in the process of the uninterrupted education concerning health and safety and involves ways and methods for realization of the system of health and safety in professional activity.

It is necessary to separate in the structure of the professional competence in the area of teacher's health and safety the following components: motivational, cognitive, activity and reflexive (Table 1).

Conclusions and Perspectives of Future Researches in the Given Area. So, the analysis of teachers' professional activity in health and safety of pupils has helped us to regulate the structure of personality-professional formation in the teachers' professional competence structure as the competence in health and safety.

In the perspective of future researches we plan to develop technology of teachers' professional competence development in health and safety in postgraduate pedagogical education and to work out basic qualimetric model of its estimation.

Table 1

The Components Characterization of the Professional Competence
in the Area of Teacher's Health and safety

Components	Characterization
Motivational	the need of systematic knowledge realizing in the area of health and safety in order to reduce children injuries; a sensible desire to gain success in the preventive pedagogical activity, the need to realize own potential; comprehension of the importance of the continuous and systemic life-long rise of professional competence.
Cognitive	knowledge of modern normative-legal base in the area of health and safety; knowledge of the primary scientific principles, fundamental laws, theories and statements of the health and safety; knowledge of demands while equipping studies, knowledge of the contents trends of health and safety; (road safety, electric- and fire safety, poisoning, explosion safety, safety in the water, first medical aid, hygienic training and child upbringing, domestic traumatism etc.), possessing the information according to the actual problems in the sphere of safety.
Activity	abilities of using normative base in practice; ability of organizing traditional and non-standard preventive measures; playing problem situations, educational work with parents dealing with the questions in the area of health and safety; the possession of various ways of intensification of the educational cognitive activity of students ability of using visual aids in the area of health and safety; ability of organizing cooperation with profile establishments and specialists in the area of safety; ability of using a preventive component of a studied subject a teacher instructs; ability of analyzing the possible risks that may endanger his life and health; ability to guarantee sticking to the sanitary-hygienic standards in teachers' professional and students' educational activity
Reflexive	possession of abilities to analyze the results of own professional development, students' activity, ability to control the students' fulfillment of safety rules, ability to control behavior in the process of teachers' professional activity, to lead a regular life.

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Астахова М. С. Компетентність з безпеки життєдіяльності як невід'ємний складник професійної компетентності вчителя. У статті розкрито сутність та зміст понять «професійна компетентність вчителя» та «компетентність з безпеки життєдіяльності» з погляду різних учених, окреслено роль вчителя у формуванні культури безпеки в учнів та функціональні компоненти педагогічної діяльності з питань безпеки життєдіяльності.

Визначено, що «професійна компетентність» – це сукупність професійних знань, умінь, а також способів виконання професійної діяльності, а «компетентність з безпеки життєдіяльності» – це інтегрована характеристика професійних і особистісних якостей спеціаліста, яка базується на сумі знань, умінь та навичок, отриманих у процесі неперервної освіти з питань безпеки життєдіяльності, та включає способи і прийоми реалізації системи забезпечення безпеки життєдіяльності в професійній діяльності.

Компетентність з безпеки життєдіяльності віднесено до групи ключових компетентностей особистості в цілому та професійних компетентностей сучасного вчителя зокрема.

Визначено сутність компетентності з безпеки життєдіяльності вчителя, зумовлену особливостями його професійної діяльності, та її структурні компоненти (мотиваційний, когнітивний, діяльнісний та рефлексивний).

Ключові слова: компетентність, безпека життєдіяльності, учитель, професійна компетентність, компетентність з безпеки життєдіяльності.

Астахова М. С. Компетентность по безопасности жизнедеятельности как неотъемлемая составляющая профессиональной компетентности учителя. В статье раскрыта сущность и содержание понятий «профессиональная компетентность учителя» и «компетентность по безопасности жизнедеятельности» с точки зрения различных ученых, очерчена роль учителя в формировании культуры безопасности учащихся и функциональные компоненты педагогической деятельности по вопросам безопасности жизнедеятельности.

Определено, что «профессиональная компетентность» – это совокупность профессиональных знаний, умений, а также способов выполнения профессиональной деятельности, а «компетентность по безопасности жизнедеятельности» – это интегрированная характеристика профессиональных и личностных качеств специалиста, которая базируется на сумме знаний, умений и навыков, полученных в процессе непрерывного образования по вопросам безопасности жизнедеятельности, и включает способы и приемы реализации системы обеспечения безопасности жизнедеятельности в профессиональной деятельности.

Компетентность по безопасности жизнедеятельности отнесена к группе ключевых компетентностей личности в целом и профессиональных компетенций современного учителя в частности.

Определена сущность компетентности по безопасности жизнедеятельности учителя, обусловленная особенностями его профессиональной деятельности, и ее структурные компоненты (мотивационный, когнитивный, деятельностный и рефлексивный).

Ключевые слова: компетентность, безопасность жизнедеятельности, учитель, профессиональная компетентность, компетентность по безопасности жизнедеятельности.

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